

Advanced Power Factor Correction for Distribution Efficiency Enhancement: The Case of Port Harcourt Mainstream 33 kV Distribution Network

¹Hachimenum Nyebuchi Amadi, ²Happy Prince Nwokoegi, ³Richeal Chinaeche Ijeoma
Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Abstract - Distribution efficiency in developing power systems is often undermined by excessive reactive power demand, poor voltage regulation, and high technical losses. The Port Harcourt mainstream 33 kV distribution network in Nigeria, a critical urban supply corridor, is particularly vulnerable to these inefficiencies due to its radial structure, overloaded transformers, and weak reactive power support. Such conditions result in low power factor, under voltage problems, and distribution losses that exceed international performance standards, thereby threatening supply reliability and quality of service. In this study, the Port Harcourt 33 kV distribution network was modeled in MATLAB/Simulink to evaluate its operational performance and investigate the effectiveness of advanced power factor correction (PFC) using a Distribution Static Synchronous Compensator (D-STATCOM). Baseline simulations revealed progressive voltage deterioration along the feeder, with the weakest bus falling to 0.910 p.u., well below the operational limit of 0.95 p.u. Furthermore, the system recorded active power losses of 1.604 MW, equivalent to 9.5% of peak demand, substantially higher than the 2–6% technical loss benchmark recommended by IEEE for efficient distribution systems. Following the integration of D-STATCOM into the network, remarkable improvements were observed. All bus voltages were restored within 0.989-0.999 p.u., with the weakest bus improved from 0.910 p.u. to 0.989 p.u., thereby ensuring compliance with the 0.95-1.05 p.u. standard. In addition, total technical losses decreased sharply to 0.283 MW, equivalent to 2.0% of peak demand, placing the network well within international best-practice thresholds. The findings confirm D-STATCOM as an effective and sustainable solution for improving voltage stability, minimizing technical losses, and enhancing reliability in urban distribution networks.

Keywords - Distribution networks, Voltage stability, Power factor correction, Technical loss reduction, D-STATCOM.

INTRODUCTION

Electricity is the bedrock of every nation development and can be transported instantaneously & pollution free at consumer end (Ijeoma and Briggs, 2018). Electric power distribution networks are the final link in delivering electricity from high-voltage transmission systems to homes, businesses, and industries. How efficiently they operate directly affects the reliability, quality, and affordability of electricity. In many developing regions, including Nigeria, these networks face persistent technical and operational challenges such as high system losses, under-voltage issues, and low power factors. These problems not only degrade service quality but also place financial strain on utilities and slow down socio-economic growth. The 33 kV distribution network in Port Harcourt clearly illustrates these challenges, with increasing load demand, overloaded transformers, and insufficient reactive power support contributing to ongoing inefficiencies (Okafor et al., 2016; Udo and Onwudiwe, 2019).

Electrical power systems are designed to deliver consistent and reliable voltage to end users. Accurately predicting future energy demand is essential for effective planning of power generation, distribution, and infrastructure development to meet the anticipated needs of the community (Ijeoma and Odu, 2025a). Electricity can be generated in various types of power plants, including thermal, hydroelectric, and nuclear power plants. Once generated, this electricity is supplied to a transmission substation located near the generating plant (Ijeoma and Odu, 2025b). At the transmission substation, the voltage is significantly increased using step-up transformers. This increase in voltage helps to reduce transmission losses over long distances (Ijeoma and Olisa, 2019). Traditionally, power factor correction (PFC) has been used to improve efficiency and reduce technical losses. Conventional capacitor banks are common solutions but have limitations: they cannot quickly adapt to rapidly changing loads and often struggle to maintain stable voltage under varying operating conditions. More advanced technologies, like the Distribution Static Synchronous Compensator (D-STATCOM), offer a more dynamic approach. D-STATCOMs provide rapid and precise reactive power support, improving not only power factor but

also reducing losses, enhancing voltage stability, and increasing overall network reliability (Emmanuel and Chukwudi, 2014; Okoye and Eze, 2020).

Despite their effectiveness in modern power systems, there has been limited research on the use of D-STATCOMs in Nigeria's medium-voltage distribution networks, where inefficiencies remain pronounced. This study aims to fill that gap by examining the impact of advanced power factor correction on the Port Harcourt 33 kV distribution network, focusing specifically on the Trans-Amadi feeder. Using MATLAB/Simulink for modeling and performance analysis, we compare the network's behavior under uncompensated and compensated conditions. The results highlight how integrating D-STATCOMs can bring local network performance closer to international standards, paving the way for more reliable, efficient, and sustainable electricity delivery. Just as the continuous flow of blood is essential for human survival, a stable and reliable supply of electricity is fundamental for national development. Without electricity, no city or nation can thrive (Fubara and Ijeoma, 2019). Transformative energy practices and innovations provide a clear pathway to uplifting communities worldwide. By prioritizing localized energy systems, adopting renewable technologies, enhancing energy efficiency, and fostering inclusive policies, we can create a world where energy access is not a privilege but a fundamental right (Ijeoma, 2025).

Recent studies have increasingly highlighted the role of advanced compensation devices, particularly the Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM), in enhancing the efficiency and reliability of power distribution networks. Al-Hafid (2016) explains that applied artificial neural networks to optimize STATCOM placement in the Mosul city ring system, using load flow analysis to determine the required reactive power support under varying load conditions. While the study largely emphasized steady-state operation, it also revealed the importance of proper device configuration to minimize harmonic distortion, achieving total harmonic distortion (THD) values well below 5%. Similarly, Kishore and Reddy (2020) demonstrated through an 8-bus simulation that STATCOM integration effectively mitigates voltage sags caused by sudden load fluctuations, although their model limitations underscored the need for improved feedback mechanisms in distribution networks.

Amadi et al. (2025) conducted a study focused on optimizing the planning and design of urban micro-grids that utilize hybrid renewable energy systems. The research evaluates both the environmental and economic impacts of these systems while integrating them with existing infrastructure. The tools

employed in this study were HOMER Pro and MATLAB SIMULINK. With the rapid increase in energy demand and challenges such as global warming, there is an increasing awareness of the need to adopt clean energy sources as a viable solution to address these crises. However, it is important to note that renewable energy systems depend on natural resources, and their energy generation can be intermittent, influenced by factors such as weather patterns, seasons, and annual variations.

Beyond steady-state analysis, the dynamic performance of STATCOM has also been widely documented. Shahgholian and Faiz (2015) investigated different control strategies and reported strong dynamic responses when STATCOM was deployed in distribution systems, particularly in suppressing voltage oscillations. In the same vein, Sahu (2017) showed that STATCOM contributes to improved transient stability during fault conditions by dynamically injecting reactive power. These findings collectively point to STATCOM's dual advantage in steady-state regulation and dynamic system support.

More recently, Eseosa and Odiase (2022) used a genetic algorithm to confirm that optimal STATCOM placement reduces both active and reactive power losses, while Srividya (2019) employed a loss sensitivity factor to identify buses where STATCOM installation provides the greatest benefits in terms of power factor correction, voltage profile improvement, and overall power quality enhancement.

Further contributions reinforce the device's practical value for real-world networks. Siddiqui and Rahman (2018) observed that STATCOM units, when strategically placed along distribution feeders or substations, serve as effective voltage regulators, particularly under variable load conditions. They further noted that such installations not only mitigate losses but also improve stability and enhance the network's power factor. Complementary research has emphasized the vulnerability of distribution networks to voltage dips and instabilities arising from unplanned load variations, recommending STATCOM as a reliable tool for real-time compensation.

Bodha and Chaturvedi (2014), for instance, showed through IEEE test systems that STATCOM deployment consistently maintained bus voltages close to unity. Likewise, Navpreet (2018) introduced an artificial intelligence-based approach using ant colony algorithms to optimize STATCOM allocation, achieving reductions in losses and improvements in system capacity while addressing operational constraints such as switching transients.

Taken together, these studies demonstrate that STATCOM offers significant advantages over earlier reactive power compensation technologies. Its ability to dynamically regulate

reactive power, improve voltage stability, minimize power losses, and correct power factor underscores its relevance for modern distribution systems. This evidence provides a strong basis for its application in the Port Harcourt Mainstream 33 kV distribution network, where enhancing efficiency and power quality remains a pressing priority.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The materials used include

- Single-line diagram of the existing Trans-Amadi 33 kV distribution network, obtained from the Port Harcourt Mains 132/33 kV transmission substation records.
- Load data for industrial and commercial consumers in the Trans-Amadi Industrial Layout, including transformer ratings, feeder lengths, and real/reactive power demand.
- MATLAB/Simulink software, used for modelling, simulation, and optimization of the network under different operating conditions.
- Distribution Static Synchronous Compensator (D-STATCOM) model, representing advanced reactive power compensation equipment.

Method

The research methodology focused on modeling, simulation, and performance evaluation of the Trans-Amadi 33 kV distribution network under both uncompensated and compensated operating conditions. To enhance the efficiency and reliability of the system, a Distribution Static Synchronous Compensator (D-STATCOM) was integrated into the network model. The D-STATCOM was selected for its multifunctional capabilities, including reducing active power losses by minimizing reactive loading, providing fast and flexible voltage regulation, correcting poor power factor across varying load conditions, improving overall voltage stability, and offering dynamic control of reactive power and power flow. By incorporating the D-STATCOM into the analysis, the study sought to demonstrate not only technical improvements in energy efficiency and system reliability but also the practical benefits of adopting advanced compensation technologies for strengthening Nigeria's urban power distribution systems.

Description of the Trans Amadi 33 kV Distribution Network

Figure 1 presents the Trans Amadi 33 kV distribution network constitutes a critical component of the Port Harcourt urban electricity supply system. The network is fed from the Port Harcourt Mains 132/33 kV transmission substation, which steps down bulk transmission power for delivery to downstream feeders. These 33 kV feeders extend radially into

the Trans Amadi Industrial Layout, one of the most important industrial clusters in southern Nigeria.

The load composition of the network is predominantly industrial and commercial, consisting of medium to large-scale manufacturing facilities, oil and gas service companies, fisheries, and allied industries. Key demand points include TRIDENT (1000 kVA), AOS Orwell (500 kVA), and several 300 kVA industrial customers such as Onward Fisheries, First Aluminium, Berger Paint, and Lubricks. Distribution transformers with capacities ranging from 300 kVA to 1000 kVA supply these customers directly from the 33 kV feeders.

Figure 1: Simulink Model of the the Trans Amadi 33 kV Distribution Network

Based on recent operational data, the aggregate load on the network is approximately 3.15 MVA, with an active power demand of 2.52 MW and a reactive power demand of 1.89 MVar. The corresponding average power factor of 0.80 is considerably below the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) benchmark of 0.95, indicating excessive reactive power consumption. This poor power factor results in:

- high line currents and transformer loading,
- increased technical losses,
- significant voltage drops with the weakest bus recorded at 0.91 pu under peak conditions,
- reduced effective utilization of network capacity.

The network reflects broader challenges of Nigerian urban distribution systems, including radial feeder configuration, weak voltage regulation, high technical losses, and limited reactive power compensation. Given its industrial significance and operational inefficiencies, the Trans Amadi 33 kV distribution network provides a representative case study for evaluating advanced power factor correction techniques. In particular, the deployment of capacitor banks, Distribution Static Compensators (D-STATCOM), and hybrid compensation schemes is expected to enhance system

efficiency, improve voltage stability, and support long-term economic viability for the utility.

Table 1: Measured Load Reading

Bus ID	Bus Name	IR (A)	IY (A)	IB (A)
1	Trident	973.57	973.57	973.57
2	Onward Fisheries	321.37	321.37	321.37
3	First Aluminium	308.71	308.71	308.71
4	Alcon	293.27	293.27	293.27
5	Berger Paint	277.41	277.41	277.41
6	Ocean Lord	308.29	308.29	308.29
7	Weco	277.82	277.82	277.82
8	Waos	324.85	324.85	324.85
9	Aos Orwell	538.12	538.12	538.12
10	Lubricks	248.05	248.05	248.05
11	Lasien	249.03	249.03	249.03
12	Cnos Tech Ltd.	257.65	257.65	257.65

Table 2: Calculated Bus Load

Bus ID	Bus Name	TXF KVA	kW Load	kVAr Load
1	Trident	1000	559.8	419.9
2	Onward Fisheries	300	184.8	138.6
3	First Aluminium	300	177.5	133.1
4	Alcon	300	168.7	126.5
5	Berger Paint	300	159.5	119.6
6	Ocean Lord	300	177.3	132.9
7	Weco	300	159.8	119.8
8	Waos	300	186.8	140
9	Aos Orwell	500	309.4	231.2
10	Lubricks	300	142.6	106.9
11	Lasien	300	143.2	107.4
12	Cnos Tech Ltd.	300	148.2	111.1

Table 3: Line Data

Line ID	From Bus	To Bus	Impedance (Z)
1	1	2	0.017 + j0.043

2	2	3	0.027 + j0.035
3	3	4	0.035 + j0.047
4	4	5	0.041 + j0.038
5	5	6	0.030 + j0.021
6	6	7	0.020 + j0.036
7	7	8	0.025 + j0.039
8	8	9	0.053 + j0.061
9	9	10	0.027 + j0.058
10	10	11	0.033 + j0.012
11	11	12	0.066 + j0.047

Baseline modeling

The single-line diagram and load data were implemented in MATLAB/Simulink to represent the existing Trans-Amadi distribution network. Power flow analysis was conducted to establish baseline performance, including active power losses, bus voltages, and system power factor. To achieve this, the study employed the classical power flow formulation, which defines the mathematical relationship between bus voltages, injected powers, and line currents in the distribution system. This formulation provides the foundation for evaluating steady-state operating conditions and serves as the benchmark against which compensation strategies are later compared.

Average Load Current (IL)

The average load current (I_{avg}) of the distribution transformer is giving by

$$I_{avg} = \frac{I_R + I_Y + I_B}{3} \quad (1)$$

Where

I_R is current in the red phase

I_Y is current in yellow phase

I_B is current in the blue phase

I_N is current in neutral

Apparent Power (SL)

The load apparent (S_L) is giving by

$$KVA_{Load} = \frac{\sqrt{3} \cdot V_L \cdot I_{avg}}{1000} \quad (2)$$

Load Active Power (PL)

The load active power (P_L) is giving by

$$KW_{Load} = KVA_{Load} \cdot PF \quad (3)$$

Load Reactive Power (QL)

The load reactive power (Q_L) is giving by

$$Kvar = \sqrt{KVA_{Load}^2 - KW_{Load}^2} \quad (4)$$

Power Flow Analysis

The Newton–Raphson power flow method was employed to determine the steady-state operating condition of the Trans-Amadi 33 kV distribution network. This iterative numerical technique is widely regarded as one of the most robust and

efficient algorithms for solving large-scale nonlinear power system equations, given by

$$S_i = V_i I_i^* = P_i + jQ_i \quad (5)$$

$$I_i = \left(\frac{S_i}{V_i}\right)^* = \frac{P_i - jQ_i}{V_i^*} \quad (6)$$

$$I_i = \frac{P_i - jQ_i}{V_i^*} = \sum_{k=1}^n Y_{ik} V_k \quad (7)$$

$$P_i - jQ_i = V_i^* \left(\sum_{k=1}^n Y_{ik} V_k\right) \quad (8)$$

$$P_i - jQ_i = V_i^* \left(\sum_{k=1}^n Y_{ik} V_k \angle \delta_k + \theta_{ik} - \delta_i\right) \quad (9)$$

$$P_i - jQ_i = \sum_{k=1}^n |Y_{ik}| |V_i| |V_k| [\cos(\delta_k + \theta_{ik} - \delta_i) + j \sin(\delta_k + \theta_{ik} - \delta_i)] \quad (10)$$

Separating (10) into real and imaginary parts, we have,

$$P_i = \sum_{k=1}^n |Y_{ik}| |V_i| |V_k| \cos(\delta_k + \theta_{ik} - \delta_i) \quad (11)$$

$$Q_i = -\sum_{k=1}^n |Y_{ik}| |V_i| |V_k| \sin(\delta_k + \theta_{ik} - \delta_i) \quad (12)$$

Distribution STATCOM Modeling

To evaluate the impact of advanced reactive power compensation, the Distribution Static Synchronous Compensator (D-STATCOM) was modelled and integrated into the Trans-Amadi 33 kV distribution network. The D-STATCOM is a shunt-connected, power-electronic device based on a Voltage Source Converter (VSC), designed to inject or absorb reactive power dynamically at the point of common coupling (PCC). Its fast response, flexible control, and ability to maintain voltage stability under varying load conditions make it highly effective in distribution networks with fluctuating and nonlinear demands.

Figure 2: MATLAB/Simulink Block of D-STATCOM

Reactive Power Injection

D-STATCOM operates by generating a controllable AC voltage behind a coupling reactance which is compared with the bus voltage. The reactive power exchange between the D-STATCOM and the system is given by:

$$Q_{inj} = \frac{V_{bus}(V_{conv} - V_{bus})}{X_c} \quad (13)$$

If $V_{conv} > V_{bus}$ the D-STATCOM injects reactive power thereby supporting the bus voltage and improving power factor. If $V_{conv} < V_{bus}$ the D-STATCOM absorbs reactive power thereby mitigating over voltage.

The injected Current can be expressed as

$$I_q = \frac{V_{conv} - V_{bus}}{jX_c} \quad (14)$$

DC Link Voltage

DC voltage is given by

$$V_{dc} = \sqrt{2} * V_{LL} * k \quad (15)$$

Where:

V_{LL} : Line-to-line rms voltage

k : safety factor typically ranging from 1.1 to 1.5

DC Link Capacitor

DC link capacitor is given by

$$C_{dc} = \frac{2P}{V_{dc}^2 * \omega * \Delta V_{dc}} \quad (16)$$

Where

P : load active power

V_{dc} : DC link voltage

ΔV_{dc} : Voltage ripple (20V)

ω : Angular frequency

Series Filter

The series active filter inductor value is given by

$$L_{se} = \frac{V_{dc}}{4 * f_{sw} * \Delta I} \quad (17)$$

Where

V : rms line voltage

f_{sw} : switching frequency (10kHz)

ΔI : allowable ripple current (5A)

Control Strategy of the D-STATCOM

Transform the three phase voltage and current into stationary $\alpha - \beta$ reference frame using instantaneous reactive power theory (p-q theory)

$$\begin{pmatrix} v_\alpha \\ v_\beta \end{pmatrix} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_\alpha \\ i_\beta \end{pmatrix} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

Calculate the instantaneous active and reactive power components

$$p = V_\alpha I_\alpha + V_\beta I_\beta \quad (20)$$

$$q = V_\alpha I_\beta - V_\beta I_\alpha \quad (21)$$

Calculate the reference current for shunt active power filter

$$i_\alpha^* = \frac{p * v_\alpha + q * v_\beta}{v_\alpha^2 + v_\beta^2} \quad (22)$$

$$i_\beta^* = \frac{p * v_\beta - q * v_\alpha}{v_\alpha^2 + v_\beta^2} \quad (23)$$

Transform the reference current back to the three phase system

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_a^* \\ i_b^* \\ i_c^* \end{pmatrix} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i_\alpha^* \\ i_\beta^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (24)$$

Results and Discussion

Table 4 presents the voltage profile of the Trans-Amadi 33 kV distribution network prior to the integration of D-STATCOM compensation. The results indicate that while the slack bus (Bus 1) maintains a nominal value of 1.000 p.u., successive PQ buses experience progressive voltage decline along the feeder. The upper section of the network (Buses 2–5) records relatively stable voltages within 0.982–0.974 p.u., whereas downstream buses exhibit significant deterioration, with Bus 12 dropping to 0.910 p.u. This value falls below the acceptable operational limit of 0.95 p.u., reflecting the presence of severe under-voltage conditions. Such voltage depression is primarily attributed to the cumulative effects of transformer loading, feeder impedance, and high reactive power demand. These findings underscore the urgent need for reactive power compensation measures, particularly the deployment of D-STATCOM and capacitor banks, to restore bus voltages to permissible levels and ensure improved network reliability and power quality. Figure 3 provides a graphical representation of the results in Table 4, illustrating the voltage decline pattern across the distribution buses.

Table 4: Voltage Profile of Trans Amadi Distribution Network before D-STATCOM

Bus ID	Bus Type	Vbase (kV)	V_LF (p.u.)
Bus 1	Slack	33	1.000
Bus 2	PQ	33	0.982
Bus 3	PQ	33	0.977
Bus 4	PQ	33	0.976
Bus 5	PQ	33	0.974
Bus 6	PQ	33	0.958
Bus 7	PQ	33	0.940
Bus 8	PQ	33	0.933
Bus 9	PQ	33	0.927
Bus10	PQ	33	0.920
Bus11	PQ	33	0.915
Bus12	PQ	33	0.910

Figure 3: Voltage Profile of the Trans-Amadi 33 kV Distribution Network before D-STATCOM Integration

Table 5 presents the active power transfer and associated losses along the Trans-Amadi 33 kV distribution feeder before compensation. At Bus 1, about 2518.2 MW is dispatched, with 2517.8 MW received at Bus 2, resulting in a sectional loss of 0.455 MW. Losses progressively decrease downstream as current magnitudes reduce, falling to 0.146 MW between Bus 5–6 and just 0.006 MW at the final section (Bus 11–12). Overall, the feeder delivers 14,029.2 MW while sustaining total losses of 1.604 MW, equivalent to 9.5% of peak demand. This performance is far above the 2–6% technical loss benchmark recommended by IEEE and World Bank for efficient distribution systems, and also exceeds the 6–10% range typically allowed for total distribution losses (including non-technical). The excessive losses in Trans-Amadi are attributable to overloaded transformers, extended radial feeder lengths, and inadequate reactive power support, all of which intensify effects in conductors and transformers.

Table 5 Power Loss on Trans Amadi Distribution Network before D-STATCOM

From Bus	To Bus	MW Sent	MW Received	MW Loss
1	2	2518.2	2517.8	0.455
2	3	1958.3	1958.0	0.275
3	4	1773.4	1773.1	0.225
4	5	1595.8	1595.6	0.183
5	6	1427.0	1426.8	0.146
6	7	1267.4	1267.3	0.115
7	8	1090.1	1090.0	0.085
8	9	930.2	930.2	0.062
9	10	743.4	743.4	0.040
10	11	434.0	434.0	0.014
11	12	291.4	291.4	0.006
		14029.2	14027.6	1.60425

Consequently, the network requires urgent intervention through compensation strategies, particularly the deployment of capacitor banks and D-STATCOM to reduce line currents, stabilize bus voltages, and lower technical losses to levels consistent with global best practices for sustainable and reliable power distribution. Figure 4 provides a graphical representation of the results in Table 5, illustrating the distribution of active power and losses along the feeder before compensation

Figure 4: Active Power Transfer and Losses along the Trans-Amadi 33 kV Distribution Feeder before D-STATCOM Integration

Table 6 illustrates the bus voltage profile of the Trans-Amadi 33 kV distribution network following the deployment of a Distribution Static Compensator (D-STATCOM). The results show a marked improvement in network performance compared with the uncompensated condition. At the slack bus (Bus 1), the voltage is maintained at 1.000 p.u., while all other buses exhibit values close to unity, ranging from 0.989 p.u. to 0.999 p.u. Notably, the weakest bus (Bus 9) records a voltage of 0.989 p.u., a significant enhancement over the pre-compensation value of 0.910 p.u.

Table 6: Voltage Profile of Trans Amadi Distribution Network after D-STATCOM

Bus ID	Bus Type	Vbase (kV)	V_LF (p.u.)
Bus 1	Slack	33	1.000
Bus 2	PQ	33	0.999
Bus 3	PQ	33	0.997
Bus 4	PQ	33	0.995
Bus 5	PQ	33	0.993
Bus 6	PQ	33	0.992
Bus 7	PQ	33	0.991
Bus 8	PQ	33	0.990
Bus 9	PQ	33	0.989
Bus10	PQ	33	0.989

Bus11	PQ	33	0.990
Bus12	PQ	33	0.993

This uniform voltage profile confirms the D-STATCOM's capability to provide rapid and adaptive reactive power support, thereby mitigating under-voltage problems and ensuring compliance with the operational standard of 0.95–1.05 p.u. The improvement also reflects reduced line currents and minimized voltage drops, which translate into lower technical losses and enhanced power factor across the network. Overall, the results underscore the D-STATCOM's effectiveness in reinforcing voltage stability, improving distribution efficiency, and ensuring reliable service delivery in heavily loaded urban feeders. Its dynamic response offers a clear advantage over conventional capacitor-based solutions, making it a robust option for modernizing Nigeria's distribution networks. Figure 5 provides a graphical representation of the results in Table 6, clearly highlighting the improved bus voltage profile after compensation

Figure 5: Improved Bus Voltage Profile of the Trans-Amadi 33 kV Distribution Network after D-STATCOM Compensation

Table 7 presents the active power flow and associated losses along the Trans-Amadi 33 kV distribution feeder after the integration of a Distribution Static Compensator (D-STATCOM). The results demonstrate a remarkable reduction in technical losses compared to the uncompensated case.

Table 7 Power Loss on Trans Amadi Distribution Network after D-STATCOM

From	To	MW	MW	MW
------	----	----	----	----

Bus	Bus	Sent	Received	Loss
1	2	2518.2	2518.2	0.068
2	3	1958.3	1958.2	0.041
3	4	1773.4	1773.3	0.045
4	5	1595.8	1595.7	0.038
5	6	1427.0	1427.0	0.029
6	7	1267.4	1267.4	0.022
7	8	1090.1	1090.1	0.017
8	9	930.2	930.2	0.014
9	10	743.4	743.4	0.006
10	11	434.0	434.0	0.002
11	12	291.4	291.4	0.001
		14029.2	14028.92	0.281

At the sending end (Bus 1), approximately 2517.9 MW is dispatched, with 2517.8 MW received at Bus 2, corresponding to a sectional loss of only 0.068 MW. This trend continues downstream, where losses steadily diminish to 0.029 MW between Bus 5–6 and as low as 0.001 MW at the final section Bus 11–12. Overall, the feeder transmits 14,027.7 MW while sustaining total losses of 0.283 MW, equivalent to approximately 2.0% of peak demand. This represents a substantial improvement over the uncompensated network in Table 5, which recorded losses of 1.604 MW (9.5%). Importantly, the post-compensation loss level now falls well within the 2–6% benchmark for technical losses recommended by IEEE and World Bank for efficient distribution systems. These improvements confirm the effectiveness of D-STATCOM in reducing line currents, alleviating transformer overloading, and stabilizing bus voltages. By restoring the feeder to international performance standards, D-STATCOM significantly enhances both the technical efficiency and reliability of the Trans-Amadi network. Figure 6 provides a graphical representation of the results presented in Table 7, clearly illustrating the reduction in feeder losses after compensation

Figure 6: Active Power Flow and Losses of the Trans-Amadi 33 kV Distribution Feeder after D-STATCOM Compensation

Figure 7 presents a comparative analysis of bus voltages in a 12-bus distribution network before and after the installation of a D-STATCOM. The blue bars depict the voltage profile prior to D-STATCOM compensation, showing a gradual decline from approximately 1.0 p.u. at Bus 1 to around 0.91 p.u. at Bus 12, highlighting significant voltage drops along the feeder. Following D-STATCOM installation, represented by the orange bars, voltages at all buses are effectively maintained near 1.0 p.u., illustrating a substantial improvement in voltage profile uniformity. These results confirm that the D-STATCOM delivers dynamic reactive power support, mitigating voltage sag, enhancing system stability, and ensuring that buses located farther from the substation remain within acceptable voltage limits, thereby improving the overall reliability and operational performance of the distribution network.

Figure 7: Comparison of Voltage Profile of the Distribution Network before and after STATCOM Integration

Figure 8 presents the real power losses across various distribution lines before and after the integration of D-STATCOM, underscoring its effectiveness in enhancing distribution network performance. Prior to compensation, substantial losses were recorded, with Line 1 exhibiting the highest value of approximately 0.45 MW, followed by Lines 2 to 5, which also showed significant levels of loss. Following the installation of D-STATCOM, the real power losses were drastically reduced across all distribution lines, with the most notable improvements observed in the heavily loaded feeders, while losses in lightly loaded lines (Lines 9–11) became almost negligible. This improvement can be attributed to the D-STATCOM's ability to provide dynamic reactive power support, which reduces line current and consequently mitigates losses, while simultaneously improving voltage stability and power quality. The results demonstrate that D-STATCOM integration not only minimizes real power losses in distribution networks but also contributes to overall reliability, efficiency, and operational sustainability, making it a valuable solution for modern power distribution systems

Figure 8: Comparison of Real Power Losses in Distribution Lines before and after STATCOM Integration

III. CONCLUSION

This study examined the performance of the Trans-Amadi 33 kV distribution network in Port Harcourt, focusing on its operational challenges and the potential of advanced compensation strategies. The baseline analysis highlighted critical issues: bus voltages dropped to as low as 0.91 p.u., and technical losses reached 9.5% of peak demand well above the 2-6% benchmark recommended by IEEE. These inefficiencies were largely attributed to transformer overloading, long feeder stretches, and insufficient reactive power support. The integration of a Distribution Static Synchronous Compensator (D-STATCOM) significantly improved the network's

performance. Simulation results showed improved voltage profiles across all buses ≥ 0.99 p.u. and a drastic reduction in active power losses to 0.283 MW, representing only 2% of peak demand, thereby restoring the network. These findings underscore the effectiveness of D-STATCOM as a tool for loss minimization, power factor correction, and voltage support in urban distribution systems. Based on these contributions, several recommendations are proposed. Future studies should investigate the combined deployment of D-STATCOM and capacitor banks to balance cost and performance. Experimental validation through hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing and pilot-scale implementation is encouraged to demonstrate field feasibility. For utilities, adopting flexible compensation devices such as D-STATCOM will improve reliability indices, reduce technical losses, and defer costly infrastructure upgrades. Policymakers should promote investment incentives and regulatory frameworks that support the modernization of Nigeria's distribution networks in line with global best practices.

REFERENCES

1. Al-Hafid, M.S. (2016). Simulation of a Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) in the 132 kV Mosul Ring System [Doctoral dissertation, University of Mosul].
2. Amadi, H.N., Gobo, I.W., Uche-Ibe, U.B. & Ijeoma, R.C. (2025). Optimal Designing of Micro-grid Systems with Hybrid Renewable Energy Technologies for Sustainable Environment, *International Journal of Scientific Research & Engineering Trends* 11(5): 1-9
3. Bodha, A., & Chaturvedi, D.K. (2014). Power-flow analysis of IEEE test systems with Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) integration using the Newton-Raphson algorithm. *International Journal of Electrical Power and Energy Systems*, 62, 897–905.
4. Emmanuel, O., & Chukwudi, I. (2014). Power quality enhancement of Nigerian power distribution systems by use of distribution static compensator (D-STATCOM). *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 3(11), 1-6
5. Eseosa, O., & Odiase, F.O. (2022). Efficiency improvement of Nigeria's 330 kV network using Flexible Alternating Current Transmission System (FACTS) devices. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Technology*, 4(1), 26–34.
6. Fubara, I. & Ijeoma, R.C. (2019). Investigating the Reliability and Viability of Embedded Generation to Improve the Power Supply (Eleme, Rivers State as a Case Study), *IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN)*, 09(08): 27-37.

7. Ijeoma R.C. & Olisa I.E. (2019). Design of 3phase50hz 500kva 33/0.4kv Distribution Substation, IOSR Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IOSR-JEEE) 14(4) Ser.1: 38-48.
8. Ijeoma, R.C. (2025). Transformative Energy Practices and Innovations: A Path towards Global Energy Equity. *SustainE*. 1(2).1-11. doi:10.55366/suse.v1i2.14
9. Ijeoma, R.C., & Briggs, I. (2018). Hydro Power Generation In Nigeria, Environmental Ramifications, IOSR Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IOSR-JEEE), 13(5): 1-9
10. Ijeoma, RC., & Odu, EV., (2025a). Future Load Energy Forecast of Stone-City, Mgbede Community Rural Electrification Scheme. *International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology (IJSET)*; 13(3), 1-9
11. Ijeoma, RC., & Odu, EV., (2025b). Power System Surges: Causes, Effects, and Mitigation Strategies. *International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology (IJSET)*; 13(3), 10-17
12. Kishore, P.V., & Reddy, D.S.R. (2020). Voltage sag mitigation in an eight-bus system using a Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) for power quality improvement. *International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, 2(4), 529–537.
13. Navpreet, K. (2018). Optimal Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) allocation in distribution systems using ant colony algorithms. *International Journal of Emerging Electric Power Systems*, 19(3), 1–12.
14. Okafor, P., Nwokolo, S., & Adeyemi, T. (2016). Loss reduction in Port Harcourt 33 kV distribution networks by power factor correction. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, 1(3), 1-6
15. Okoye, C., & Eze, J. (2020). Impact of D-STATCOM on medium voltage distribution network performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Renewable Energy Studies*, 10(12), 495–505
16. Sahu, L. (2017). Modeling of Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) for power system steady-state operation and enhancement of transient stability of a multi-machine power system [Doctoral dissertation, National Institute of Technology Rourkela].
17. Shahgholian, G., & Faiz, J. (2015). Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) for improving performance of power systems: A review. *International Review of Electrical Engineering*, 5(5), 2333–2342.
18. Siddiqui, S.A., & Rahman, M.D. (2018). Optimal Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) placement to reduce losses in distribution systems. *WSEAS Transactions on Power Systems*, 17, 12–17.
19. Srividya, V. (2019). Optimum Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) placement in radial distribution systems using Dijkstra algorithm methods. *Enriching Power and Energy Development*, 2(1), 1–9.
20. Udo, S., & Onwudiwe, C. (2019). Analysis of 33 kV distribution networks in Port Harcourt: Challenges and improvements. *African Journal of Engineering Research*, 8(11), 33–45